

Auto-tuning 2D Stencil Applications on Multi-core Parallel Machines

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Abstract

On multi-core clusters or supercomputers, how to get good performance when running high performance computing (HPC) applications is a main concern. In this report, performance oriented auto-tuning strategies and experimental results are presented for stencil HPC applications on multi-core parallel machines. A typical 2D Jacobi benchmark is chosen as the experimental stencil application. The main tuning strategies include data partitioning within a multi-core node, number of threads within a multi-core node, data partitioning for a number of nodes, number of nodes in a multi-core cluster system. The results of the experiments are based on multi-core parallel machines from PRACE or Grid'5000, such as Curie, and Stremi cluster.

1. Introduction

With the increasing development of multi-core and Petascale or even Exascale supercomputers, scalability is a one of the key issues for high performance computing. On a given multi-core cluster system, how to obtain the highest speedup is a main concern for HPC applications. One may ask: can the ideal scenario be implemented by using the maximum number of nodes and the maximum number of cores in a given multi-core cluster system? For some benchmarks, such as Linpack [1], the answer may be “YES”. While for real HPC applications, the answer is very complicated, especially on diverse heterogeneous multi-core clusters and Petascale supercomputers. So, we conduct research on some tuning strategies for the execution of a selected stencil HPC application on multi-core clusters (from Grid'5000) and multi-core based Petascale supercomputers (from PRACE). A 2D Jacobi benchmark as well as a real NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) [2] application were chosen as typical stencil HPC applications. As a first step, we just present the experimental results for the Jacobi benchmark in this report.

The fundamental issue is how to make data partitioning and run the application on a number of nodes on a multi-core cluster or supercomputer with good performance. There are a lot of running parameters to select, which are not obvious for end users. An auto-tuning framework is beneficial to the execution of the application. After the analysis of the specific application and probing of resources, running parameters are evaluated on the basis of tuning algorithms and training. Then we can run the application with optimized parameters. Finally, we get the performance results and feedback. For the parameters, we explore two levels: node level and system level. The main tuning strategies include data partitioning within a multi-core node, number of threads or processes within a multi-core node, data partitioning for many nodes, number of nodes in a multi-core cluster system.

2. Jacobi benchmark

Stencil codes are most commonly found in the codes of computer simulation in the context of scientific and engineering HPC applications. To run an application on a multi-core node or a multi-core cluster, it needs domain decomposition or data partitioning. Jacobi is one of the notable examples of domain decomposition and stencil computation. As a first benchmark application, we adopted a 2D Jacobi iteration application (5 points) for the experiments. Generally speaking, given an initial matrix A, the new value is the mean value of its four neighbors and stored in another temporary equal-size matrix B. This can be described as the following equation.

$$B(i, j) = 0.25 * (A(i - 1, j) + A(i, j - 1) + A(i + 1, j) + A(i, j + 1))$$

Let's define S_x , S_y as the sizes of the 2D array. S_x is set to be equal to S_y . After the calculations, Matrix A is covered with

Matrix B. This is repeated for many iterations. Although it is a simple benchmark, it is useful for a basic analysis and evaluation of performance auto-tuning on multi-core machines.

3. Resource model of multi-core cluster systems

There are various architectures for multi-core cpus. For the resource model of multi-core cluster systems, firstly, we give some definitions to describe the basic characteristics of multi-core cluster machines. The definitions of multi-core node level and multi-core cluster level are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Definitions of resource model of multi-core cluster systems

Definitions of multi-core node level		Definitions of multi-core cluster level	
Nc	The maximum number of cores	Nt	Total number of available nodes
Ns	Number of sockets	Nn	Number of nodes (variable)
C1	Capacity of Level 1 cache	Tt	Total running time of the application
Bc1	Level 1 cache bandwidth	Te	Computation time of the application
C2	Capacity of Level 2 cache	Tc	Communication time of the application
Bc2	Level 2 cache bandwidth	Bn	Network bandwidth
C3	Capacity of Level 3 cache	Ln	Network latency
Bc3	Level 3 cache bandwidth	Nbs	The best number of nodes for speedup
Cn	Capacity of Level n cache		
Bcn	Level n cache bandwidth		
Cm	Capacity of memory		
Bm	Memory bandwidth		
Lm	Memory latency		
Tbs	The best number of threads for speedup		

4. Performance tuning of the 2D Jacobi benchmark on multi-core machines

The data partitioning policy, the number of threads per node, and the number of nodes have an obvious impact on the performance of running stencil applications on multi-core cluster systems. The performance tuning strategies are described as follows.

4.1 Data partitioning within a multi-core node

For the 2D Jacobi benchmark, it needs data partitioning when running the application with multiple threads. So, each thread can deal with a part of the Jacobi array. There are 3 main policies, i.e. data partitioning by row, data partitioning by column, data partitioning by both of row and column. For data partitioning by both of row and column, there are some more choices with different number of rows and columns on the basis of factorization. If implementing the Jacobi benchmark with C/C++, because the data of array are stored in the memory by row, usually, it can bring a better performance with data partitioning by row. Conversely, for the implementation with Fortran, it is more efficient to partition data by column due to data storage in the memory by column.

4.2 Number of threads within a multi-core node

With the increase of the number of cores on a chip, there are dozens or even hundreds of cores within one multi-core node. While memory bandwidth per socket may remain constant, memory per core may decrease. So, how to choose the number of threads is a practical issue when running multi-threaded applications. For some benchmarks, such as Linpack, one usually uses the maximum number of cores as the number of MPI processes within a multi-core node. However, it is complicated for the real applications, especially for memory bandwidth sensitive applications.

As shown in our previous study [3] for the Jacobi application, the performance of multi-threads and multi-processes are almost the same within a multi-core node. To predict the best number of threads or processes within a given multi-core node, we need some more definitions. Let $Bm1$ be the required memory bandwidth with a single thread, which is calculated as the ratio of transferred data to the estimated transferring time. For the provided memory bandwidth of the multi-core node, Bm (memory bandwidth) is the measured effective memory bandwidth on the basis of stream benchmark [4]. So, Tbs (the best number of threads for speedup) equals the minimum number between the predicted number of threads before saturating memory bandwidth

and the maximum number of cores. For the estimation of $Bm1$, prefetching is not considered as the data sizes we are considering are larger than the cache sizes. The measured run time is defined as the sum of data transfer time and computation time. The computation time is calculated on the basis of total floating point operations of the Jacobi benchmark and the effective capability of one CPU core (estimated based on the efficiency of Linpack). Thus, the following formulas are simplified as we neglect overlaps between computation and data transfer.

$$Bm1 = \text{TransferredData} / \text{TransferTime} \text{ (MB/s)}$$

$$\text{TransferredData} = (S_x * S_y) * \text{Sizeof}(\text{Double})$$

$$\text{TransferTime} = \text{Measured_Run_Time} - \text{TotalFlop_of_Application} / (\text{PeakFlops_of_one_core} * \text{Efficiency_of_Linpack})$$

$$T_{bs} = \text{Min.}(Bm / Bm1, Nc)$$

4.3 Data partitioning for many nodes

The 2D Jacobi benchmark also needs data partitioning when running the application on many nodes (one core per node or multiple cores per node). Then, each node can deal with a part of the Jacobi array. The 3 main data partitioning policies are the same with those within one multi-core node. However, it usually brings a better performance with data partitioning by both of row and column, especially, in the case of one core per node, as it decreases the communication volume. The number for dividing rows (X) and the number for dividing columns (Y) should be as close as possible to the square root of N_n .

$$X = \text{Maximize} V, \text{ such that } N_n \bmod V = 0, 1 \leq V \leq \sqrt{N_n}; Y = N_n / X$$

Currently, we can only run NEMO application based on MPI processes. In the case of multiple cores per node, the performance of hybrid MPI processes and Pthreads is almost the same as that of plain MPI processes for the Jacobi benchmark [3]. So, in the context of this report, we will just use plain MPI processes for the experiments. N_n is set to be the total number of MPI processes.

4.4 Number of nodes in a multi-core cluster system

For the Jacobi application, the following formulas are simplified models based on the definitions given in Table 1. It is assumed that a good domain decomposition is adopted for efficient communication. Just as described in Table 1, T_t is total running time of the application, T_e is computation time of the application, and T_c is communication time of the application. They are calculated in the following equations.

$$T_t = T_e + T_c \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

$$T_e = K1 * S_x^2 / N_n \quad (\text{K1 is a constant})$$

$$T_c = K2 * S_x / \sqrt{N_n} + L_n \quad (\text{K2 is a constant})$$

$K1$ is the computation time of one cell of the array normalized with respect to the number of used cores within one node.

$K2$ is the communication time for a unit of double-precision data.

$$K2 = \text{Sizeof}(\text{Double}) / B_n$$

For example, the network bandwidth is typically 1 Gb/s, 20 Gb/s, or 40 Gb/s for a multi-core cluster. B_n is the measured effective network bandwidth. $K2$ is calculated on the basis of effective network bandwidth.

The estimated optimal number of nodes (N_n') is required to minimize the total running time. At the same time, for the sake of feasible data partitioning, N_n' should not be larger than $S_x * S_x$. The predicted best number of nodes for speedup (N_{bs}) is the minimum value between N_n' and the total number of available nodes (N_t). For this Jacobi benchmark, N_n' is the minimum value between $S_x * S_x$ and N_t . Latency would finally limit the speedup if increasing the number of nodes infinitely.

$$N_{bs} = \text{Min.}(N_n', N_t)$$

4.5 Auto-tuning for all the strategies

The parameters to be tuned include different data partitioning strategies, different number of threads or processes per node, and different number of nodes. The optimization space of each parameter is listed in Table 2. On the basis of the enumerated possible optimization space, we provide a hierarchical auto-tuner that explores this optimization space for multi-core nodes of the experimental machines, and for multi-core clusters at a reduced concurrency corresponding to the specific machines, e.g. 128 nodes on Curie thin nodes. In the training step, the best parameters are determined with a small scale of computing resources on a specific machine, then a runtime script (not source code) will be automatically generated for the stencil application on a specific machine. So, the input parameters of the specific application and a specific multi-core cluster system include S_x , S_y , N_c , B_m , $Bm1$, PeakFlops of one core, N_t , B_n , $K1$. The output running parameters include T_{bs} , N_{bs} , X , Y for data partitioning.

Table 2. Some parameters space for performance auto-tuning

Category	Parameter Name	Parameter tuning space by machine					
		Sagittaire	Graphene	Griffon	Stremi	Curie thin	Curie xlarge
Multi-core node	Data partitioning within a multi-core node	by row (X=1, Y=#_of_threads) by column (X=#_of_threads, Y=1) by both with different # of rows and columns (X={2...Nc/2}, Y={2...Nc/2}, XY=#_of_threads)*					
	# of threads per node	{1...2}	{1...4}	{1...8}	{1...24}	{1...16}	{1...128}
Multi-core cluster	Data partitioning for many nodes	by row (X=1, Y=Nn) by column (X=Nn, Y=1) by both with different # of rows and columns (X={2...Nn/2}, Y={2...Nn/2}, XY=Nn)*					
	# of nodes	{1...79}	{1...144}	{1...92}	{1...44}	{1...2800}	{1...76}

*X is the number for dividing rows, Y is the number for dividing columns of the Jacobi array; #_of_threads means number of threads (not more than Nc).

5. Experiments and Results

5.1 Experimental setup

A summary of the architectures of the evaluated systems is shown in Table 3. They are typical HPC/supercomputing systems from Grid'5000 and PRACE. Sagittaire, Graphene, Griffon and Stremi clusters are from several grid sites of Grid'5000. Curie (Bull) is located at CEA/TGCC-GENCI. Multi-core nodes include Intel Xeon L5420, L5335, Intel Nehalem-EX X7560, AMD Opteron 6164, varying from 2 cores to 128 cores per node. Multi-core processors often involve some levels of cache sharing. The memory varies in capacity and bandwidth. The communication networks include Infiniband, Myrinet, and Gigabit Ethernet. As the machines span a variety of multi-core processor and network technologies, the auto-tuning strategies need to deliver performance portability across them.

Sagittaire (Grid'5000-2 cores per node)

Sagittaire is a Sun system with 79 nodes built from AMD Opteron processors. There are 2 sockets per node. Each socket has just 1 core with a private 64 KB L1 cache, a private 1 MB L2 cache and 1 GB memory. So each node has 2 GB memory. The interconnection network is Gigabit Ethernet.

Graphene (Grid'5000-4 cores per node)

Graphene is a "Carri" system with 144 nodes, which is built from Intel Xeon processors. There is just 1 socket per node, 4 cores per socket. Each core has a private 32 KB L1 cache and a private 256 KB L2 cache. Each node shares a 8 MB L3 cache and 16 GB memory. Each node has an Infiniband 20 Gb card and a Gigabit Ethernet card.

Griffon (Grid'5000-8 cores per node)

Griffon is a also "Carri" system with 92 nodes, which is built from Intel Xeon processors. There are 2 sockets per node, 4 cores per socket. Each core has a private 32 KB L1 cache. 2 cores share a 6 MB L2 cache. Each node shares 16 GB memory. Each node also has an Infiniband 20 Gb card and a Gigabit Ethernet card.

Stremi (Grid'5000-24 cores per node)

Stremi is a HP Proliant system with 44 nodes built from AMD Opteron processors. There are 24 cores per node. Each node has 2 sockets, 12 cores per socket. Each core has a private 64 KB L1, and a private 512 KB L2 cache. 6 cores share a 5 MB L3 cache and 12 GB memory. Each node has 48 GB memory. The interconnection network is Gigabit Ethernet.

Curie nodes (PRACE-16/32/128 cores per node)

CURIE is a BULL x86 system based on a modular and balanced architecture of thin (5040 blades, each with 2 sockets, 8 cores per socket based on the Intel SandyBridge processor), large (360 "fat nodes", each with 4 sockets, 8 cores per socket and 128 GB of memory) and hybrid (144 blades, each with 288 NVIDIA M2090 GPUs) nodes with more than 360 TB of distributed memory and 15 PB of shared disk. The interconnection network is Infiniband QDR full fat tree network. In 2012, fat nodes have been transformed to be 76 extra-large nodes. Each extra-large node contains 128 cores and has 512 GB of memory. There are 4 groups within a node. Each group is just like a fat node, which has 4 sockets, and each socket has 8 cores. Each core has a private 32 KB L1 and a private 256 KB L2 caches. 8 cores in a socket share a 24 MB L3 cache and 32 GB memory. Altogether, each node has 512 GB of memory. For the 5040 "thin" blades, there are 2 sockets per node, each socket has 8 cores. Each core also has a private 32 KB L1 cache and a private 256 KB L2 cache. 8 cores in a socket share a 20 MB L3 cache and 32 GB memory. Each node has 64 GB memory.

We carried out the following sets of experiments for the study:

- (1) Stream benchmark within a multi-core node.
- (2) Jacobi benchmark application: different data partitioning policies within a multi-core node; different data partitioning policies for many nodes (including 1 core per node and some cores per node); we run the Jacobi application with different configurations, e.g. increasing the number of threads within a multi-core node (1 node, some threads or processes), increasing the

number of nodes within a supercomputer (some nodes and 1 process per node), the same number of nodes with increasing number of processes on each node (a given number of nodes, some processes per node), and different number of nodes with increasing number of processes per node (some nodes and some processes per node).

Table 3. Overview of evaluated multi-core cluster systems

System		AMD Opteron 250 (Lyon Sagittaire)	Intel Xeon L5335 (Nancy Graphene)	Intel Xeon L5420 (Nancy Griffon)	AMD Opteron 6164 HE (Reims Stremi)	Intel Xeon E5-2680 (Curie thin nodes)	Intel @ Nehalem-EX X7560 (Curie fat nodes)	Intel @ Nehalem-EX X7560 (Curie xlarge nodes)
Core -Level	Type	AMD Opteron	Intel Xeon	Intel Core 2	Opteron 6100	Intel xeon	Intel Nehalem	Intel Nehalem
	Processor	90nm	65nm	45nm	45nm	32nm	45nm	45nm
	Clock(Ghz)	2.4	2.53	2.5	1.7	2.7	2.26	2.26
	DP Gflop/s	9.6	10.12	10	6.8	21.6	9.04	9.04
	Instruction set	32bit	64-bit	64-bit	64bit	64bit	64bit	64bit
	L1 Data Cache/core	64KB	32KB	32KB	64KB	32KB	32KB	32KB
	L2 Cache/core	1MB	256KB	-	512KB	256KB	256KB	256KB
Node -Level	Shared L2/L3 cache	-	8MB(shared by 4 cores)	6MB(shared by 2 cores)	5MB(shared by 6 cores)	20MB(shared by 8 cores)	24MB(shared by 8 cores)	24MB(shared by 8 cores)
	# sockets	2	1	2	2	2	4	16
	Cores/Socket	1	4	4	12	8	8	8
	Total cores	2	4	8	24	16	32	128
	DP(Peak) Gflop/s	19.2	40.48	80	163.2	345.6	289.28	1157.12
	Linpack Gflop/s	-	-	-	-	281.7*	243.06*	972.24*
	Stream Triad Bandwidth per node (GB/s)	3.7	11.78	6.22	30.48	88.53	62.82	251.28
	Stream Triad Bandwidth per core (GB/s)	1.85	2.95	0.78	1.27	5.53	1.96	1.96
	DRAM Capacity	1GB*2 = 2GB	16GB	16GB	12GB*4= 48GB	32GB*2= 64GB	32GB*4= 128GB	32GB*4*4= 512GB
	DRAM Capacity/core	1GB	4GB	2GB	2GB	4GB	4GB	4GB
	FSB	-	1333 MHz	1333 MHz	3200 MHz	QPI :8GT/s (4000MHz) DMI:5GT/s	QPI : 6.4GT/s	QPI : 6.4GT/s
	ChipPower (Watts)	89W	50W	50 W	65W	130W	130W	520W
System -Level	# nodes	79	144	92	44	5040	180	76
	Compiler	gcc 4.4.5	gcc 4.4.5	gcc 4.4.5	gcc 4.4.5	gcc 4.4.5	gcc 4.4.5	gcc 4.4.5
	Network	Gigabit Ethernet	Infiniband-20G and Gigabit Ethernet	Infiniband-20G and Gigabit Ethernet	Gigabit Ethernet	Fat Tree Infiniband	Fat Tree Infiniband	Fat Tree Infiniband
	Year	-	-	-	-	2011	2011	2012

*source: top500 website[5]; for others, the default efficiency of Linpack is set to be 90%.

5.2 Stream memory benchmark

Gflops, memory bandwidth, I/O, and network are very important for the performance of multi-core cluster systems. In our first study for the Jacobi benchmark and the GYRE configuration of NEMO application, I/O is not a bottleneck problem. Memory bandwidth is a prominent factor for the performance in a multi-core context. We used the stream benchmark[4] to get the basic memory bandwidth data of the machines with different multi-core architectures. For the stream benchmark, the Triad loop ($a(i) = b(i) + q*c(i)$) has memory access to 3 double precision words (24 bytes) and two floating point operations (one

addition and one multiplication) per iteration. We chose “Triad” as the metric of evaluation for the memory bandwidth of the multi-core machines.

Figure 1. Memory bandwidth on the basis of stream benchmark (left: Grid5000-clusters; right: Prace-Curie supercomputers)

Figure 1 shows the memory bandwidth in function of threads on the experimental platforms. Since each test runs 10 times, only the best time for each is used. There is little difference with repeated experiments. So we do not use error bars in the figure. We used cyclic mapping and block mapping policies for the mapping of threads of Stream benchmark onto cores. Compared with block mapping, cyclic mapping usually brings a better bandwidth improvement with the increasing of number of threads on a multi-core node. Groups or sockets may determine the memory bandwidth, e.g. the step-wise increase of bandwidth for stremi block mapping indicates that groups of 6 cores sharing L3 cache is determining the memory bandwidth. Within a 6 core group, memory bandwidth may be saturated before using 6 threads, the memory access is uniformed with a cyclic mapping spread over all sockets.

5.3 Measured performance of Jacobi benchmark

5.3.1 Different data partitioning policies within a multi-core node

Figure 2. Computation time of Jacobi benchmark with different data partitioning policies on one node of Stremi cluster

Figure 3. Computation time of Jacobi benchmark with different data partitioning policies on one node of Curie xlarge nodes

To show the impact on performance of data partitioning policies within a multi-core node, two multi-core nodes (24 cores and

128 cores per node) were chosen for the experiments. Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the measured performance results with different data partitioning policies within one node on the 24-core node of Stremi cluster and 128-core node of Curie xlarge nodes respectively. In the figures, (X*Y) means the data partitioning method, X is the number for dividing rows, Y is the number for dividing columns of the Jacobi array. Just as expected, partitioning by row usually brings a better performance for the codes implemented in C++, in particular on a large multi-core node.

5.3.2 Different number of threads within a multi-core node

Figure 4. Performance of Jacobi benchmark with increasing number of threads within one multi-core node. (left: 4-core node on Graphene cluster; right: 8-core node on Griffon cluster)

Figure 5. Performance of Jacobi benchmark with increasing number of threads within one multi-core node. (24-core node on Stremi cluster)

Figure 6. Performance of Jacobi benchmark with increasing number of threads within one multi-core node. (left: 16-core node on Curie thin nodes; right: 32-core node on Curie fat nodes)

We tested all of the possible number threads to have a comprehensive understanding of the correlation between the performance and the number of threads within a multi-core node. In the above figures, for a given array size (22016*22016), we present the measured speedup of Jacobi benchmark application in function of threads on the experimental platforms. Figure 4

shows the results of the 4-core node and 8-core node from Nancy Graphene and Griffon clusters. Figure 5 shows the results of the 24-core node from Reims Stremi cluster. Figure 6 shows the results of the 16-core node and 32-core node from Curie thin and fat nodes. There is a good correspondence between the prediction model and measurement, which will be shown in Section 6.2. For another given size (22528*22528), Figure 7 shows the results of the 128-core node from Curie xlarge nodes. Here we used random mapping of threads, the behavior of block mapping or cyclic mapping was almost the same. From the figures, we can see that in many cases using the maximum number of cores for the number of threads can bring the best speedup compared with other number of threads. But in some other cases, they tell a different story. For example, in the 128-core node, 71 is a measured best number of threads for the speedup. It was mainly due to the saturation of memory bandwidth with the increasing number of threads. The predicted optimal number of threads is 74, the performance impact will be presented in Section 6.2. At the same time, the errorbars in the 128-core node are large, which needs a further study of the threads mapping policies. The efficiency is prone to decrease with the increasing of number of threads within a multi-core node.

Figure 7. Performance of Jacobi benchmark with increasing number of threads within one multi-core node. (128core-node on Curie xlarge nodes)

Figure 8. Computation time of Jacobi benchmark with different data partitioning policies for 96 processes on 4 nodes of Stremi cluster

Figure 9. Computation time of Jacobi benchmark with different data partitioning policies for 128 processes on 128 nodes of Curie thin nodes

5.3.3 Different data partitioning policy for many nodes

We present two examples to show the impact on performance of data partitioning policies in the multi-core clusters. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the measured performance results for different data partitioning policies on 4 nodes (24 processes per node) in the Stremi cluster and on 128 nodes (1 process per node) in the Curie large nodes respectively. In the figures, (X*Y) also means the data partitioning method, X is the number for dividing rows, Y is the number for dividing columns of the Jacobi array. For 1 process per node, just as expected, it usually brings a better performance with data partitioning by both of row and column, and the number of rows and columns should be as close as possible to the square root of Nn (number of nodes). For multiple processes per node, there were some small deviations for the performance.

5.3.4 Different number of nodes on a multi-core cluster

Figure 10. Performance of the Jacobi benchmark for 3 different data sizes with increasing number of nodes on Curie thin nodes (1 process per node)

Figure 11. Performance of the Jacobi benchmark for 3 different data sizes with different number of nodes and increasing number of processes on Curie thin nodes (N.P: N is the number of nodes and P is the number of processes per node).

We used Curie thin nodes for the experiments of many multi-core nodes.

Figure 10 shows the computation time and speedup of the Jacobi benchmark application with increasing number of nodes (some nodes and 1 process per node). There is a good scalability with the increasing of number of nodes. In some cases, it even brought a better speedup than the linear speedup. This is due to the contribution of cache for the partitioned data.

Figure 11 shows the computation time and speedup of the Jacobi benchmark with different number of nodes and increasing

number of processes (some nodes and some processes per node). Given the number of nodes, in many cases, the performance improves with the increasing number of processes on each node. It means that the speedup usually increases with the total number of processes. In some cases, there is an exception when using the maximum number of cores per node. There may be a performance decrease compared with less number of processes per node.

For the same total number of processes, using different number of nodes with increasing number of processes per node (given the total number of processes, some nodes and some processes per node) shows that the performance usually decreases with the increasing number of processes on each node. It means that usually one process per node can bring a good performance. It is mainly due to the contention of memory bandwidth, when increasing the number of processes within one multi-core node. Basically, the smaller the number of processes per node is, the better the performance will be. During the experiments presented in Figure 11, we obtained the best speedup when using 8192 processes with 2048 nodes and 4 processes per node.

6. Evaluation of the performance tuning strategies

6.1 Tuning of data partitioning policy within a multi-core node

Just as described in Section 4.1, there are many choices for the data partitioning policies within one multi-core node. For two examples, we present the comparison between the predicted best data partitioning policy with measured best data partitioning policy within one multi-core node. Table 4 shows the performance results on the 24-core node of Stremi cluster and 128-core node of Curie xlarge nodes respectively. Basically, the predicted best data partitioning policy by row can bring the best performance. While there were also some exceptions, e.g. for the size of 22016*22016 on a Curie xlarge node (128 cores), dividing the rows into two parts (by both of row and column) was the best choice. The performance impact was about 20.1%.

Table 4. Comparison of predicted best data partitioning policy and measured best policy within one multi-core node (for speedup of Jacobi benchmark)

Jacobi benchmark	Stremi (24 cores)			Curie xlarge (128 cores)		
	predicted	measured	performance impact	predicted	measured	performance impact
10240*10240 (104857600)	By row (1*24)	By row (1*24)	0%	By row (1*128)	By row (1*128)	0%
14848*14848 (220463104)	By row (1*24)	By row (1*24)	0%	By row (1*128)	By row (1*128)	0%
20480*20480 (419430400)	By row (1*24)	By row (1*24)	0%	By row (1*128)	By row (1*128)	0%
22016*22016 (484704256)	By row (1*24)	By row (1*24)	0%	By row (1*128)	By both of row and column (2*64)	20.1%
23040*23040 (530841600)	By row (1*24)	By row (1*24)	0%	By row (1*128)	By row (1*128)	0%

6.2 Tuning of number of threads within a multi-core node

Table 5. Comparison of predicted best number of threads and measured best number of threads within one multi-core node (for speedup of Jacobi benchmark)

Jacobi application	Stremi (24cores)			Curie thin (16cores)			Curie fat (32cores)			Curie xlarge (128cores)		
	predicted	measured	perf. impact	predicted	measured	perf. impact	predicted	measured	perf. impact	predicted	measured	perf. impact
4096*4096 (16777216)	24	24	0%	16	12	3.1%	32	31	3.5%	-	-	-
10240*10240 (104857600)	24	24	0%	16	12	1.3%	32	31	1.5%	74	119	21.4%
20480*20480 (419430400)	24	24	0%	16	14	0.6%	32	32	0%	75	81	12.9%
22016*22016 (484704256)	23	24	0.3%	16	14	0.6%	32	32	0%	-	-	-
23040*23040 (530841600)	22	24	2.1%	16	12	0.8%	32	32	0%	74	71	10.1%

("-": for a faster completion of the execution on the 128-core node, some data sizes were skipped)

The best number of threads is not always the maximum number of cores on each experimental platform, especially for the

large number of cores. To run a specific application on various multi-core platforms, just as described in Section 4.2, we used the functions to predict the best number of threads for speedup (Tbs) on the basis of the basic characteristics of the resource model and the application. So it does not need to test all of the possible number of threads for the training. For the Jacobi benchmark application, Table 5 shows the comparison between the predicted best number of threads for speedup and the measured best number of threads within one node. On the 2-core node from Sagittaire cluster and 4-core node from Graphene cluster as well as 8-core node from Griffon cluster, there were no deviations. They are not listed in Table 5. On the other multi-core nodes, the predicted best number of threads is basically similar with the measured best number of threads. In some cases, there are some deviations. The performance impacts were usually less than 3.5%. For the 128-core Curie xlarge node, there are comparatively larger performance impacts due to the NUMA nature, when the measured best number of threads is not the maximum number of cores within one multi-core node. In this case, the performance impacts were between 10.1% and 21.4%.

6.3 Tuning of data partitioning policy for many nodes

Table 6. Comparison of predicted best data partitioning policy and measured best policy on many multi-core nodes (for speedup of Jacobi benchmark)

Jacobi application	96 processes on Stremi cluster (4nodes, 24cores/node)			128 processes on Curie xlarge nodes (128nodes, 1core/node)		
	Size	predicted	measured	perf. impact	predicted	measured
4096*4096 (16777216)	By both of row and column (8*12)	By both of row and column (8*12)	0%	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (8*16)	0%
10240*10240 (104857600)	By both of row and column (8*12)	By both of row and column (6*16)	6.2%	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (8*16)	0%
14848*14848 (220463104)	By both of row and column (8*12)	By both of row and column (3*32)	1.9%	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (4*32)	0.5%
20480*20480 (419430400)	By both of row and column (8*12)	By both of row and column (8*12)	0%	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (16*8)	6.1%
22016*22016 (484704256)	By both of row and column (8*12)	By both of row and column (6*16)	1.5%	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (8*16)	0%
23040*23040 (530841600)	By both of row and column (8*12)	By both of row and column (6*16)	2.1%	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (8*16)	0%

Just as described in Section 4.3, there are also many choices for the data partitioning policies on the multi-core cluster. The training step was conducted at a reduced concurrency, e.g. 128 nodes on Curie thin nodes. We present two examples of the comparison between the predicted best data partitioning policy with measured best data partitioning policy on multi-core clusters. Table 6 shows the performance results on 4 nodes (24 processes/node) in the Stremi cluster and 128 nodes (1 process/node) in the Curie thin nodes respectively. In many cases, the predicted best data partitioning policy by both of row and column (the number of rows and columns should be as close as possible to the square root of Nn) can bring the best performance. But, there were some more deviations compared with the prediction within one multi-core node, especially for the scenario of multi-processes per node. The performance impacts were up to 6.2%.

6.4 Tuning of number of nodes on a multi-core cluster

Currently, for many real HPC applications, including NEMO [2], increasing the number of nodes can not always bring a better performance. There may be a limitation for the speedup. Jacobi benchmark is one of the few HPC applications which can scale well in theory. For the Jacobi benchmark, Table 7 shows the comparison between the predicted best number of nodes for speedup and the measured best number of nodes on Curie thin nodes. In many cases, it has a good scalability. However, there were also some deviations, the performance impacts were up to 14.9%. So, in some cases, there may be a limitation in practice, which needs a further analysis of the resource model and the specific application.

Table 7. Comparison of predicted best number of nodes and measured best number of nodes on Curie thin nodes (for speedup of Jacobi benchmark)

Jacobi array size	Predicted best # of nodes on Curie thin nodes	measured best # of nodes on Curie thin nodes	performance impact
1024*1024(1048576)	2800	2800	0.0%
4096*4096(16777216)	2800	2800	0.0%
10240*10240(104857600)	2800	1024	14.9%
14848*14848(220463104)	2800	2048	11.7%
20480*20480(419430400)	2800	2800	0.0%

6.5 Evaluation of all the strategies

Table 8 Comparison of predicted best parameters and measured best parameters for performance auto-tuning on Curie thin nodes (for speedup of Jacobi benchmark)

Category	Parameter Name	Jacobi size							
		4096*4096 (16777216)		10240*10240 (104857600)		14848*14848 (220463104)		20480*20480 (419430400)	
		predicted	measured	predicted	measured	predicted	measured	predicted	measured
Multi-core node	Data partitioning within a multi-core node	By row							
	# of threads per node for one node	16	12	16	12	16	12	16	14
	Performance impact	3.1%		1.3%		0.9%		0.6%	
Multi-core cluster	Data partitioning for many nodes (128 nodes)	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (4*32)	By both of row and column (8*16)	By both of row and column (16*8)				
	# of nodes	2800	2800	2800	1024	2800	2048	2800	2800
	Performance impact	0.0%		14.9%		11.7%		0.0%	

Currently, on a multi-core cluster or supercomputer, one may choose a number of nodes according to the problem size of the application and the available number of nodes on a given supercomputer. And there may be a constraint for the number of nodes on some machines. To obtain the best performance, all of the parameters need to be tuned. On the Curie thin nodes (with a large scale of nodes), Table 8 shows the comparison of predicted parameters for the best performance with the measured parameters for the best performance. In this case, the performance impacts within a multi-core node were just up to 3.1%. In many cases, the results on multi-core clusters show good scalability of the Jacobi benchmark. In some cases, the performance impacts on a multi-core cluster were comparatively larger than those within a multi-core node. The prediction methods may be improved.

7. Conclusion and Future works

In this report, we have presented some tuning strategies, prediction methods and experimental results of auto-tuning to obtain good performance when running stencil HPC applications on multi-core clusters or supercomputers. Most of the performance results came from a typical 2D Jacobi benchmark. They show that the tuning strategies are important and useful for performance optimization of the stencil computations. In many cases, the results of predictions were in accordance with those of comprehensive experiments, yet there were also some deviations for the performance, i.e. speedup. Future works include the improvement of prediction functions, threads placement policies within a multi-core node, and more experiments for the NEMO application.

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